

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION AND NEW PEDAGOGICAL APPROACHES

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Abstract

The article analyzes the reforms in the education system of the country and their importance, issues of raising inclusive education, the pedagogical significance of the concept of development of inclusive education in the public education system in 2020-2025.

Keywords

education, forms of education, inclusive education, UNCPRD, UNICEF, pedagogical analysis, method, social policy.

INKLYUZIV TA'LIM VA YANGI PEDAGOGIK YONDASHUVLAR

Annotatsiya

maqolada mamlakatimiz ta'lim tizimidagi islohotlar va ularning ahamiyati, inklyuziv ta'limni yuksaltirish masalalari, 2020-2025 yillarda xalq ta'limi tizimida inklyuziv ta'limni rivojlantirish kontseptsiyasining pedagogik ahamiyati tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar

ta'lim, ta'lim shakllari, inklyuziv ta'lim, UNCRC, UNICEF, pedagogik tahlil, metod, ijtimoiy siyosat.

At the 72nd session of the UN General Assembly in September 2017, the proposal put forward by our president was: "on Youth Rights".

An international convention was drafted. "Youth rights are, above all, the rights of Ulama to live peacefully and healthy and to receive education. ...it is always a priority for us to ensure that our young generation, growing up, grows up competently, receives quality and excellent education"[1].

According to the provisions of Article 41 of the general Committee and Article 5 of the law "on education" in the new edition (September 23, 2020), all equal rights in education[2]. This law differs from the previous version even with the introduction of the concept of inclusive(harmonized) education, and the Cabinet of

Ministers is established as the competent body in the field of inclusive education in accordance with buqonun. In this regard, it is important to equally develop the inclusive form of education in our country.

The term inclusive, meaning English - harmonization, collaborative education, is recognized by the entire world community as the most humane and most effective education. Inclusive education is the provision of equal access to science in educational institutions, taking into account the special educational needs and differences in individual capabilities for all students.

At the moment, the recognition of inclusive education in all countries will not depend only on whether the law is issued. The most important thing is to combat discrimination (separation of people) and social prejudice. That is, in recognition of inclusive education, the conduct of propaganda and propaganda among the population is the first issue in Gaul.

Since 1990, several world-wide declarations and decisions have been made regarding the education of children with special needs in the system of general educational institutions. They were recognized by many countries of the world. In 2006, the UN Convention on the rights of Persons With Disabilities (UNCPRD) was adopted. It was ratified by our country on February 27, 2009. Article 24 of this convention states: "the participating states recognize the right of people with disabilities to education. States participating ensure inclusive education and lifelong training at all levels for the purposes of exercising this right without discrimination and on the basis of equality of opportunity".[3]

Analysis and preliminary evaluation of children with disabilities in the Republic of Uzbekistan began in 1966. In November 1996, on the initiative of the National Commission of Uzbekistan for UNESCO Affairs, a national training program on "inclusive methods in special education" was successfully implemented in Tashkent. October 1998 in Bukharaa regional conference on this topic was organized. This conference was carried out in cooperation with UNESCO, UNICEF (UN children's fund), the World Health Organization and the International Labour Organization. As a result of these events, the Resource Center for Inclusive Education was established under the Ministry of public education of Uzbekistan in 2001. To date, several training seminars have been held by this center.

The project" inclusive education for children with special needs in Uzbekistan " has been implemented since 2014 to date, within the framework of which more than 900 boys and girls with special needs were involved in general education in schools, preschool educational institutions. Members of the medical, psychological

and pedagogical Commission and pedagogical staff were trained in the field of education in terms of inclusive service. Five pilot resource centers were established in different regions of our country, providing educational and methodological, legal, advisory support for children with special needs, their parents, experts. The creation of educational modules "fundamentals of inclusive education", "children with special needs in general education", "organization of an inclusive school" made it possible to further improve the educational process in this direction, improve the professional skills of pedagogical workers. The support of children in need of inclusive education as a result of limited physical capacity, the development and implementation of the necessary conditions and mechanisms for their socialization are the spiritual function of the country before its citizens. On the basis of the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 13, 2020 "on measures to further improve the education system for children with special educational needs" PQ-4860, the concept of the development of inclusive education in the public education system in 2020-2025 was approved. By completing the tasks set out within the concept, the following results are expected:

- the role of inclusive education as a strategic factor in the development, rehabilitation, integration into society of individuals with special educational needs is confirmed;
- the integrity of the educational environment of children with special educational needs is strengthened, the necessary conditions are provided for their integration into society;
- mechanisms are created to coordinate the interests of the state, society, the individual in the field of inclusive education;
- the general convenience, continuity, quality of education, as well as the level of development, flexibility and variability of students are achieved in the system of inclusive education;
- interaction within the framework of international relations in the field of inclusive education will be strengthened;
- they are supported by the state so that students receive quality education, taking into account the specificity of educational needs;
- through the gradual introduction of inclusive education, specialized educational institutions are optimized for children with special educational needs, ensuring the education of students studying in general educational institutions as a member of an equal society;
- training of personnel on the basis of inclusive education programs is established in higher educational institutions of pedagogical orientation;

-the material and technical base of inclusive educational institutions will be improved;

- full connection of inclusive educational institutions to the internet network is ensured;

- in inclusive educational institutions, a mechanism for the provision of public services is introduced for the admission of students and transfer to other educational institutions.[4]

Inclusive education ensures that people with disabilities are educated alongside their social peers, providing for (if there are no serious reasons for their development) admission to regular schools. Children with acute disabilities are in some cases educated using correctional programs in special schools and special rehabilitation centers or special classes under regular schools. The provision of education in these schools is of course provided for the implementation of the child taking into account the need.(l-app).

Together with a number of useful aspects of inclusive education, we can see a number of its disadvantages that affect its effectiveness in the table below. (Appendix 2

Benefits Disadvantages

Equal rights for all students, regardless of their ability and capabilities, the lack of a material and technical base for the implementation of Inclusive Education

The individual support of the tutor in the teaching process is the lack of trained educators, psychologists and other specialists necessary for children with special needs

The standard curriculum for acquiring social and communicative skills for children with special needs is not suitable for children with certain needs, so it requires revision and modernization

Getting a quality education and in the future-the opportunity to study at the University, master the profession, become a full-fledged and independent member of society. Teachers objectively assess the knowledge of children with special needs, so knowledge assessment is often not correct

Ordinary children will have the opportunity to develop human qualities such as empathy, patience, tolerance healthy children and a friendly and often hostile attitude towards people with disabilities from their parents Many reforms are being carried out in our country to baratraf these shortcomings.

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